

Sensitivity analysis in photodynamics: How the electronic structure controls *cis*-stilbene photodynamics?

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Abstract

The techniques of computational photodynamics are increasingly employed to unravel reaction mechanisms and interpret experiments. However, inaccuracies in nonadiabatic dynamics can lead to misinterpretations, particularly when calculated observables exhibit low sensitivity to the underlying dynamics. This issue is exemplified in the photochemistry of *cis*-stilbene, where similar experimental outcomes have been differently interpreted based on the electronic structures supporting nonadiabatic dynamics. This study examines the predictions of *cis*-stilbene photochemistry using trajectory surface hopping methods coupled with various electronic structures (OM3-MRCISD, SA2-CASSCF, XMS-SA2-CASPT2, and XMS-SA3-CASPT2) and assesses their ability to interpret experimental observations. Although the excited-state lifetimes show consistency, ranging from 360 fs to 295 fs, the reaction quantum yields vary significantly. The quantum yield for cyclization ranges from nearly zero to 35% while the photoisomerization channel can either exceed 50% or be entirely suppressed completely in the second case. Intriguingly, the calculated photoelectron signal is not strikingly different

for different reaction scenarios, making the methods seemingly reliable when treated separately. Furthermore, analyzing stationary points on the potential energy surface does not reliably predict simulation outcomes, nor does it aid in selecting a specific method before simulations. Therefore, we advocate for incorporating sensitivity analyses in the simulation protocol. While employing an ensemble of methods is impractical, nonadiabatic simulations with external bias present a resource-efficient approach to achieve this goal.

1 Introduction

Nonadiabatic dynamics simulations are increasingly becoming a standard in the theoretical chemistry toolkit, yet their reliability and best practices remain topics of ongoing debate within the field.¹ Recent discourse has underscored the sensitivity of these simulations to both electronic structure and quantum dynamics algorithms, revealing significant disparities, particularly across different electronic structure methodologies.^{2,3} This sensitivity was starkly highlighted in a recent theoretical prediction challenge, where various research teams attempted to forecast the outcomes of ultrafast electron diffraction experiments on cyclobutanone before their execution.⁴ The resulting theoretical predictions exhibited a broad spectrum of lifetimes and quantum yields, thereby challenging the predictive capacity of the *ab initio* computational photodynamics. Building upon this broader dialogue, the present study delves into a series of photodynamical simulations focusing on *cis*-stilbene isomerization. Our objective is twofold: first, to scrutinize the predictive capabilities of nonadiabatic simulations, and second, to discuss standards for conducting such simulations.

Stilbene stands out as an exceptionally suitable molecule for both experimental investigations and theoretical modeling of photoisomerization. Notably stable, it does not fragment upon photoisomerization, exhibiting primary photodynamics within hundreds of femtoseconds. In its ground state, the molecule exists in two isomeric configurations: *cis*-stilbene (also known as *Z*-stilbene in systematic nomenclature) and *trans*-stilbene (or *E*-stilbene), as

illustrated in Figure 1. *Trans*-stilbene represents the global minimum on the potential energy surface, being approximately 8.27 kJ/mol more stable than *cis*-stilbene (as calculated at the XMS-SA3-CASPT2(2,2)/cc-pVDZ level). Under normal conditions, *trans*-stilbene crystallizes while *cis*-stilbene exists in a liquid state at ambient temperature and pressure. Another noteworthy stable yet energetically disadvantaged isomer of stilbene is 4a,4b-dihydrophenanthrene (DHP) which can be generated photochemically.⁵⁻¹⁰ Both stable isomers of stilbene exhibit strong absorption in the UV region owing to the optically allowed $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. Upon excitation, *trans*-stilbene persists in the excited state for tens of picoseconds, probably being trapped in the near-planar S_1 minimum. In contrast, *cis*-stilbene undergoes decay over several hundreds of femtoseconds; a phenomenon of interest given the relatively minor energy disparity between the two isomers.¹¹⁻¹⁵

Figure 1: Chemical formulae of *trans*-stilbene, *cis*-stilbene and 4a,4b-dihydrophenanthrene.

Significant insights on *cis*-stilbene photochemistry emerged from classical photochemical studies providing an abundance of experimental quantum yields and lifetimes in gas and liquid phases and various solvents, see Table 1 for summary of measured data. Further experiments based on time-resolved spectroscopies elucidated the mechanism and atomic details underlying the photoisomerization or cyclization.¹⁶⁻²³ The pulse shape effect on quantum yields was also investigated experimentally.²⁴ This vast experimental data collection was supplemented by extensive computational studies. Range of approaches including time-dependent density functional theory,^{25,26} multireference wave function methods²⁷⁻²⁹ improved with second-order perturbation theory,^{18,30} semiempirical methods,³¹ and molecular mechanics valence bond method³² were employed in the scrutiny of *cis*-stilbene photochemistry. Despite the impressive array of experimental and theoretical methodologies, the picture of *cis*-stilbene's

photodynamics is still not converged.

Table 1: Experimental measurement of *cis*-stilbene photoisomerization quantum yields $\phi_{\text{photoisom.}}$ to *trans*-stilbene, cyclization quantum yields $\phi_{\text{cyc.}}$ to DHP, and the excited-state lifetimes τ .

Environment	$\phi_{\text{photoisom.}}$	$\phi_{\text{cyc.}}$	τ (fs)
polar solvents	0.35–0.39 ^{33,34}	0.05–0.08 ³³	380–500 ³³
nonpolar solvents	0.32–0.35 ³³	0.15–0.19 ³³	1000–1650 ³³
liquid phase	–	–	1200 ³¹
gas phase	0.04 ¹⁸	0.41 ¹⁸	320–500 ^{12,18,31,35,36}

From the large collection of works presented above, we will single out the three most recent and detailed works.^{16,18,31} These works present cutting-edge time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy experiments combined with high-level theoretical modeling that brought comprehensive accounts on timescales, quantum yields, and mechanism of *cis*-stilbene photochemistry. However, the interpretations of the measured data, which is strongly supported by the nonadiabatic dynamics simulations, differ significantly. All three works rely on a different electronic structure method, in all three cases well justified from static investigations of potential energy surfaces or literature, yet the forecasted quantum yields are discernibly inconsistent. Let us now review them briefly.

Martínez et al. applied the vacuum ultraviolet time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy to unmask the *cis*-stilbene phantom state.¹⁶ The work was supported by previous *ab initio* multiple spawning simulations in conjunction with a complete active space self-consistent field wavefunction to simulate the process, revealing a timescale of 520 femtoseconds and a minor yield of DHP formation of approximately 4%.²⁷

Wörner et al. conducted the experiments in both the gas and liquid phases (using the liquid microject technology).³¹ The experiment was backed up by Landau–Zener surface hopping dynamics with the multi-reference configuration interaction method and semiempirical OM3 Hamiltonian. The simulations predicted 52% photoisomerization quantum yield and no DHP formation supporting the claims of Martínez et al.

The work by Suzuki et al. reported a similar investigation solely in the gas phase.¹⁸

Although the excited-state populations inferred from different sets of experiments were comparable, Suzuki et al. suggested a significant formation of DHP in the gas phase (exceeding 40%), accompanied by an almost complete suppression of the photoisomerization channel. This suggestion was mainly inferred from nonadiabatic dynamics on complete active space second-order perturbation theory potential energy surfaces.

The comprehensive summary above demonstrates that the interpretation of time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy, to date, heavily relies on the theoretical elucidation of the acquired data. This observation prompts a critical question: to what extent can contemporary theory effectively guide ultrafast time-resolved experiments, and what is the predictive capacity of these methods? The choice of the electronic structure method poses seemingly a significant challenge.

In this work, we closely inspect the three electronic structure methods used for nonadiabatic dynamics in the aforementioned works^{16,18,31} demonstrating the sensitivity of dynamics to fine details of electronic structure method. We supplement an investigation of their potential energy surfaces and discuss how predictive these static pictures can be. Finally, we propose that a sensitivity analysis should become a standard component of photodynamics simulations, where a diverse portfolio of electronic structure methods is employed. While the use of an ensemble of electronic structure methods is a viable strategy, leading to improved results,³⁷ it is not always practical. We advocate for exploring cost-effective alternatives for conducting this sensitivity analysis.

2 Methods

Electronic structure methods For the ground-state sampling, we employed the Møller–Plesset perturbation theory of second order (MP2) in combination with a 6-31g* basis. Molecular optimization and frequency analysis were done using Gaussian 09, Revision D.01.³⁸

For dynamical simulations and mapping of the potential energy surfaces, we use three

different multireference approaches: state-averaged complete active space-self consistent field approach (SA-CASSCF), extended multi-state complete active space perturbation theory (XMS-CASPT2), and a multireference configuration interaction with singles and doubles (MRCISD) method based on the semiempirical OM3 Hamiltonian. The SA-CASSCF and XMS-CASPT2 methods consider the active space of two electrons in two π and π^* orbitals, further denoted as (2,2). This choice was motivated by previous studies^{16,18} and the prohibitive cost of larger active spaces. On the other hand, the OM3-MRCISD method is efficient enough to be coupled to the full active space such as (12,17) used in reference 31. A level shift of 0.25 atomic units was applied for the XMS-CASPT2 method. The SA-CASSCF and XMS-CASPT2 calculations were performed in the BAGEL package³⁹ while OM3-MRCISD in the MNDO v7.0 code.⁴⁰ The conical intersections were optimized with the gradient projection algorithm of Bearpark et al.⁴¹ for SA-CASSCF and XMS-CASPT2 in the BAGEL package and with the penalty function algorithm of Ciminelli et al.⁴² for OM3-MRCISD in the MNDO code.

Two basis sets were applied for SA-CASSCF and XMS-CASPT2 to demonstrate the basis set effect: SVP and cc-pVDZ coupled to their counterparts for density fitting SVP-jkfit and cc-pVDZ-jkfit. Both basis sets were used in previous computational studies.^{16,18} The difference between them is not large; they both are of a double- ζ quality containing the same types of basis functions but they differ in exponents, coefficients, and number of primitive Gaussians used for the core s orbitals (cc-pVDZ uses more of them). The OM3-MRCISD uses a parametrized minimal basis set.

Nonadiabatic dynamics Since this work focuses on photoisomerization of *cis*-stilbene from the bright S_1 state, the simulations were set up accordingly. All simulations were initiated in the S_1 state with geometries and momenta sampled from the harmonic Wigner distribution around the MP2/6-31g* minimum of *cis*-stilbene, assuming the temperature of 298.15 K. The CASSCF and XMS-CASPT2 dynamics were performed using the fewest

switches surface hopping (FSSH) scheme.⁴³ The OM3-MRCISD dynamics used the Landau–Zener surface hopping (LZSH) method.⁴⁴ For all simulations, the time step was set to 5 a.u. The simulations were performed using our molecular dynamics code ABIN.⁴⁵

Fewest switches surface hopping The FSSH algorithm provides the expression for the evolution of the electronic amplitudes, denoted as $c_k(t)$ where k is an electronic-state label. The evolution of the amplitudes is described by following coupled equations

$$\frac{dc_k(t)}{dt} = -\frac{i}{\hbar}c_k(t)E_k(t) - \sum_l \mathbf{F}_{kl}(\mathbf{R}(t)) \cdot \mathbf{v}(t)c_l(t), \quad (1)$$

where $E_k(t)$ represents the electronic energy of the k -th state, $\mathbf{R}(t)$ denotes the nuclear configuration following classical trajectory, $\mathbf{v}(t)$ is the nuclear velocity vector and \mathbf{F}_{kl} is the nonadiabatic coupling between states k and l , given by

$$\mathbf{F}_{kl} = \langle \psi_k | \nabla_{\mathbf{R}} | \psi_l \rangle. \quad (2)$$

Utilizing the electronic amplitudes and nonadiabatic couplings, the probability of an electronic transition (hopping) is evaluated as

$$P_{l \rightarrow k}^{FS} = \max \left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{|c_l|^2} \text{Re}(c_k c_l^*) \mathbf{F}_{kl}(\mathbf{R}(t)) \cdot \mathbf{v}(t), 0 \right). \quad (3)$$

This probability is calculated at each time step, and if a transition occurs, the gradients used for the dynamics are subsequently altered. To enforce the total energy conservation of the trajectory, the momentum is always rescaled along the nonadiabatic coupling vector upon hopping between electronic states.

Landau–Zener surface hopping In contrast to the FSSH approach, the LZSH scheme is based on an analytically solved model of linearly crossing potential energy surfaces and does not require nonadiabatic couplings for computing the transition probabilities. The

hopping probability within the LZSH scheme is evaluated only at the time t^* when a minimum between the electronic states is encountered along the trajectory. The hopping probability is then expressed as⁴⁶

$$P_{l \rightarrow k}^{LZ} = \exp \left(-\frac{\pi}{2\hbar} \sqrt{\frac{\Delta E_{lk}(\mathbf{R}(t^*))^3}{\left. \frac{d}{dt} E_{lk}(\mathbf{R}(t)) \right|_{t=t^*}}} \right), \quad (4)$$

where E_{lk} denotes the energy difference between the two electronic states l and k . To ensure total energy conservation, the momentum is also rescaled upon hopping; however, in this case, it is along the momentum vector as nonadiabatic couplings are not computed in the LZSH scheme. The LZSH technique was proven of comparable quality to FSSH for systems with well-defined conical intersections.^{2,44}

Analysis of the surface hopping trajectories One of the immediate outcomes of the dynamics is the time-dependent electronic-state populations. The population of a given state at a time t was calculated as a ratio of trajectories in that state and the total number of trajectories alive at the specified time. Since populations can be modeled as a random variable sampled from a binomial distribution (or a sum of variables from the Bernoulli distribution) at each time, we can estimate the confidence intervals using normal distribution as $ERR(t) = \pm z \sqrt{p_k(t)(1 - p_k(t))/N(t)}$, where $N(t)$ is the number of trajectories alive at given time and $p_k(t)$ is the k -th state population. Considering a two-sided 95 % confidence interval, we use $z = 1.96$ (the 97.5 % quantile of standard normal distribution). To obtain the excited state lifetime, we fit the populations with a delayed exponential function p_{fit} of the form

$$p_{\text{fit}}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & t \leq t_0 \\ \exp\left(\frac{t-t_0}{t_1}\right) & t > t_0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where t_0 (vibrational relaxation before the decay) and t_1 (exponential decay lifetime) are fitted parameters. The total lifetime τ is then $\tau = t_0 + t_1$.

Moreover, we analyzed the quantum yields of *cis*-stilbene, *trans*-stilbene and DHP. The

quantum yields are calculated as a ratio of trajectories in a specified conformation and the total number of trajectories alive at the specified time. The conformations were categorized using the geometric parameters in Figure 2. The *trans*-stilbene is defined as a conformation with $90^\circ < \theta < 270^\circ$, while DHP is a conformation with $R < 1.8 \text{ \AA}$. If none of the former conditions are met, then the conformation is categorized as *cis*-stilbene. Both the time-dependent populations and quantum yields were convolved with a Gaussian kernel using a standard deviation of 30 fs.

Figure 2: Geometric parameters R and θ used for categorizing the *cis*-stilbene, *trans*-stilbene and DHP.

Finally, we analyzed the hopping geometries employing the multidimensional scaling (MDS) algorithm that allowed us to visualize geometries in low dimensional space. The MDS algorithm takes the molecular geometries as input (set of $3N$ coordinates) and returns reduced coordinates sorted by the variance covered in the initial data. The dimensionality reduction in MDS attempts to preserve distances between the data points. We can then visualize these coordinates in arbitrary dimensional space. In this work, we will focus on the reduction to a 2-dimensional space. A more in-depth description of MDS can be found in references 2,47.

Modeling the time-resolved photoelectron spectra To describe the time-resolved photoelectron spectrum (TRPES), we extracted the photoelectron signals at every 12 fs (500 a.t.u.) along each trajectory. The ionization energies were calculated for the first 10 ionized states at the OM3-MRCISD(10,7) level, while the intensities of these ionization energies were modeled by taking norms of the corresponding Dyson orbitals (Dyson norms)

calculated at the CASSCF(2,2)/SVP level of theory. A histogram was constructed from the ionization energies weighted by their corresponding intensities at the given time, which was then convolved with a two-dimensional Gaussian kernel having a standard deviation σ of 0.1 eV in the energy domain and 22 fs in the time domain. Additionally, a cutoff for the convolution is implemented at a value of 4σ . The resulting two-dimensional heat maps the final photoelectron spectra.

3 Results and discussion

We first briefly describe the topology of *cis*-stilbene potential energy surface, focusing on the distinctions between different electronic structure levels. Next, we compare the outcome of dynamical simulations for the different electronic structure methods, with a specific focus on time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy. Finally, we suggest a thrifty approach to investigate the sensitivity of the photodynamical simulations with respect to the electronic structure method used.

3.1 Mapping the potential energy surface

The overall picture of the *cis*-stilbene photodynamics is shown in Figure 3. Following the excitation, there are two possible pathways: *i*) The cyclization pathway starts by moving towards a shallow *cis* S_1 minimum characterized by a short distance $R \approx 2.0 \text{ \AA}$ defined in Figure 2. Note that the very existence of this minimum was previously discussed in literature.^{19,48} The *cis* S_1 minimum geometry is very close in energy to a conical intersection leading to DHP ($R \approx 1.8 \text{ \AA}$). In the vicinity of this conical intersection, *cis*-stilbene can transfer its population to the ground state and either produce cyclic DHP or recover the initial *cis* structure. *ii*) The second possible pathway – photoisomerization pathway – leads to a twisted geometry with the two rings perpendicular to each other (i.e. geometry halfway between *cis* and *trans* isomers). From this minimum, four different conical intersections

are available either via one-bond flip (OBF) or hula-twist (HT): coined OBF1, OBF2, HT1, and HT2 in the literature.^{49,50} We adopt the notation used in the literature that OBF1 and HT2 funnel towards the *trans*-stilbene (denoted as *trans* CIs) while OBF2 and HT1 lead rather to the *cis* isomer (denoted as *cis* CIs). We note that this classification might be a bit arbitrary and all the conical intersections may lead to both isomers. Nonetheless, all the conical intersections are energetically accessible following the S_1 excitation of *cis*-stilbene and the molecule then funnels the excited-state wavepacket back to the ground state, either back into the *cis*-stilbene or to the *trans*-stilbene.

Figure 3: Reaction mechanism of *cis*-stilbene upon excitation to the S_1 state.

We shall now focus on the difference between the electronic structure methods applied for nonadiabatic dynamics of *cis*-stilbene in this and previous works. We zoomed the Franck-Condon point, S_1 minima, and conical intersections to compare their relative energies and discuss the plausibility of the two pathways introduced above from the energy perspective, see Figure 4. From a general perspective, all the methods predict both pathways – cyclization and isomerization – energetically accessible. The pictures drawn by XMS-SA3-CASPT2, SA2-CASSCF, and OM3-MRCISD are qualitatively comparable: the cyclization pathway being seemingly barrierless as the DHP conical intersection is below or at the level of

the *cis* minimum while the twisted minimum sits below the conical intersections in the photoisomerization pathway. XMS-SA2-CASPT2 stands as an outlier here. The DHP conical intersection is about 0.8 eV above the *cis* minimum, suggesting a discrimination of cyclization. On the other hand, one of the conical intersections in the photoisomerization pathways is discernibly below the twist minimum.

Figure 4: Mapping important point at the potential energy surface of *cis*-stilbene for various electronic structure methods. The ground state *cis*-stilbene geometry is set as a reference to 0 eV. We were not able to optimize the *cis* S_1 min geometry for the OM3-MRCISD method, as it always slipped to the conical intersection. Thus, we provide the energy calculated at the XMS-SA3-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ geometry in light purple in the bottom left panel.

Although energetics in Figure 4 can disclose the energetic accessibility of channels, it contains no information about the direction where the molecule will be driven after the excitation. To estimate how the molecule will evolve after excitation, we evaluated the potential curves along linear interpolation in internal coordinates between *cis* and *cis* S_1

minimum, and *cis* and twisted S_1 minimum, see Figure 5. These LIICs capture both reaction pathways and should help us assess if any of them will be preferred. All the methods show a very similar slope towards both reaction pathways without any seeming preference. The only outlier is again the XMS-SA2-CASPT2 method which exhibits a barrier towards the isomerization and one could assume that cyclization will be the leading pathway (which is, however, hindered by the energetic barrier of conical intersection). Although this barrier might be as well an artifact of the linear interpolation, the current investigation would

Figure 5: Linear interpolation in internal coordinates between the ground-state *cis*-stilbene geometry, twisted S_1 minimum and *cis* S_1 minimum. All the geometries were optimized at their respective electronic structure levels. The motion from the *cis* geometry to the *cis* S_1 minimum is characterized by shortening the distance R (defined in Figure 2) while the motion for *cis*-stilbene towards the twisted S_1 minimum corresponds to prolonging the distance R . As we could not optimize the *cis* S_1 minimum with OM3-MRCISD, we used a geometry close to the DHP conical intersection instead. We also plot the LIIC between *cis* OM3-MRCISD geometry and XMS-SA3-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ *cis* S_1 minimum in dashed line.

probably exclude XMS-SA2-CASPT2 from nonadiabatic dynamics application even though corresponding CASSCF calculation was used and the choice looks reasonable for an essentially two-state problem.

3.2 Nonadiabatic dynamics of *cis*-stilbene: control by electronic structure

The examination of the potential energy surfaces above offers insight into the accessibility of potential reaction pathways and hints of initial motion upon excitation to the S_1 state. Our investigation showed no preferential pathway for XMS-SA3-CASPT2, SA2-CASSCF and OM3-MRCISD – the methods applied in works of Suzuki et al,¹⁸ Martínez et al,²⁷ and Wörner et al³¹ – and we cannot claim any of them superior to others and best suitable for dynamics. The only outlier is the XMS-SA2-CASPT2 which we included in the set to test the effect of the stabilizing third state in state averaging of XMS-SA3-CASPT2. Although we would not recommend XMS-SA2-CASPT2 for dynamics, we still performed the dynamics to reveal the disparities.

First, let us examine the excited-state lifetimes, see the first column of Figure 6. The excited-state populations are not directly measurable, yet these quantities can be inferred from time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopic. Gas-phase experiments agree on excited-state lifetimes of about 320-500 fs.^{12,18,31,35,36} The calculated electronic populations (as well as the corresponding experimental data) were best fitted to a delayed exponential function, see formula 5, with a total lifetime τ . We were able to extract meaningful excited-state lifetimes only for the OM3-MRCISD ($\tau = 321$ fs), SA2-CASSCF/SVP ($\tau = 360$ fs), XMS-SA3-CASPT2/SVP ($\tau = 329$ fs) and XMS-SA3-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ ($\tau = 295$ fs) methods since XMS-SA2-CASPT2 with both basis sets did not decay to the ground state. The calculated values generally appear shorter than in the other theoretical works, yet they are still within the experimental range, see Table 2. This discrepancy may stem from differences in ground-state sampling with our simulation having more energy at the beginning. While the

extracted lifetimes appear similar across methods, the decay profiles differ significantly. For instance, the SA2-CASSCF/SVP method exhibits rapid decay, while featuring a relatively long induction period. Conversely, the XMS-SA3-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ method is characterized by a short induction period and relatively long decay time.

Figure 6: Analysis of nonadiabatic simulations for *cis*-stilbene. The left column shows the time evolution of ground and excited-state populations upon the excitation, with accompanying 95% confidence intervals and a least squares fit for the excited-state curve. The middle column tracks the distance R between C_2 and $C_{2'}$ atoms throughout the simulation period. We delineate three distinctive distances: the upper one, at 5.375 \AA , corresponds to the *trans*-stilbene structure; the middle distance, at 3.125 \AA , signifies the *cis*-stilbene configuration; and the distance at 1.8 \AA represents the DHP state. The right column showcases the *cis*, *trans*, and DHP quantum yields during the dynamics. The *trans*-stilbene is defined as a conformation $90^\circ < \theta < 270^\circ$, where θ is the dihedral angle between atoms C_1 , C_0 , $C_{0'}$ and $C_{1'}$. DHP is a conformation with $R < 1.8 \text{ \AA}$, where R is the distance between C_2 and $C_{2'}$. Any remaining configurations are classified as *cis*-stilbene.

Table 2: Calculated quantum yields ϕ and excited-state lifetimes τ together with the experimental values in various solvents and in the gas-phase. The XMS-SA2-CASPT2 simulations did not acquire enough ground-state population for evaluating either quantum yields or the lifetime. The experimental gas-phase quantum yields were omitted as they are not purely experimental quantities but were predicted on the support of simulations with XMS-SA3-CASPT2(2,2)/cc-pVDZ electronic structure.

Level of Theory	ϕ_{cis}	ϕ_{trans}	ϕ_{DHP}	τ (fs)
OM3-MRCISD (LZSH)	0.52 ± 0.04	0.48 ± 0.04	0.00 ± 0.00	321 ± 10
SA2-CASSCF/SVP	0.29 ± 0.06	0.68 ± 0.06	0.03 ± 0.02	360 ± 6
XMS-SA2-CASPT2/SVP	–	–	–	–
XMS-SA2-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ	–	–	–	–
XMS-SA3-CASPT2/SVP	0.55 ± 0.15	0.15 ± 0.11	0.3 ± 0.11	369 ± 12
XMS-SA3-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ	0.55 ± 0.14	0.02 ± 0.04	0.43 ± 0.14	295 ± 10
XMS-SA3-CASPT2(2,2)/cc-pVDZ ¹⁸	0.55 ± 0.14	0.04 ± 0.10	0.41 ± 0.14	572 ± 16
OM3-MRCISD(12,17) ³¹	0.48	0.52	0.0	≈ 500
SA2-CASSCF(2,2)/6-31G* ²⁷	0.45 ± 0.04	0.52 ± 0.04	0.04 ± 0.01	520 ± 40
Experiment (solvents) ^{33,34}	0.47-0.59	0.35-0.39	0.05-0.08	380-1650

The XMS-SA2-CASPT2 method, utilizing two different basis sets, represents very different dynamics. The molecule relaxes in the excited state without approaching closely the conical intersection resulting in minimal population transfer to the ground state within the simulation time frame. Such behavior is not surprising, referring to the previous section, where we showed the substantial energy gap between the *cis* minimum and the CI_{DHP} .

The differentiation between the various electronic structure methods is further elucidated in the middle panel of Figure 6, which now illustrates the distance R between key carbon atoms of the two benzene rings. Despite the closely matched lifetimes observed (except for XMS-SA2-CASPT2), significant differences in structural evolution manifest between the methods. In both the SA2-CASSCF and OM3-MRCISD simulations, molecules predominantly maintain *cis* configurations initially (based on the distance R), transitioning gradually to adopt *trans* geometries. Conversely, all CASPT2 calculations exhibit a shortening of the distance R and evolve towards CI_{DHP} . Subsequently, XMS-SA3-CASPT2 simulations progress to the ground state and form DHP, while XMS-SA2-CASPT2 simulations remain confined in the excited S_1 basin without culminating in the final product formation.

This narrative gains further depth when considering the time-dependent quantum yields of various products. We focus on three primary products of the photoreaction: *cis*-stilbene, *trans*-stilbene, and DHP. Again, simulations conducted at different levels of theory yield significantly divergent results. The quantum yield of DHP remains negligible with OM3-MRCISD, SA2-CASSCF, and XMS-SA2-CASPT2 levels of theory. Conversely, the XMS-SA3-CASPT2 methods exhibit a substantial quantum yield of DHP and almost no *trans*-stilbene. Considering that XMS-SA2-CASPT2 simulations did not show significant deexcitation, it is unsurprising that the majority of products consist of *cis*-stilbene. Specific values along with experiment comparison can be seen in Table 2

The potential energy surfaces in Figure 5 suggested no preference for either photoisomerization or cyclization pathways. Hence, one could expect the wave packet to bifurcate equally into those pathways. Unequal bifurcation into the pathways was already demonstrated in Figure 6. To further investigate this bifurcation, we track the evolution of the dihedral angle θ along the carbon backbone $C_1-C_0=C_0'-C_1'$, see Figure 7. Compared to the distance R , which defines the distance between the benzene rings, the dihedral θ is significantly floppier. It is apparent that the double bond can change configuration even without significant motion of the heavy benzene rings. The analysis in Figure 7 indicates that the double bond first twists to 90 degrees for all methods before settling into the *cis*, *trans*, or DHP configurations.

Figure 7: Analysis of nonadiabatic simulations for *cis*-stilbene. The left column tracks the dihedral angle θ between C_1 , C_0 , C_0' and C_1' atoms throughout the simulation period. The right column showcases the ratios of *cis* and twist geometries during the simulation period. Twist conformation is defined as a conformation with $50^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$, while the *cis* S_1 min has $10^\circ < \theta < 30^\circ$.

Finally, we applied the MDS algorithm to visualize the hopping geometries for simulations with different potential energy surfaces (see method section for details). The first two reduced coordinates plotted in Figure 8 cover the majority of variance in the data while preserving distances between the geometries as much as possible. MDS was applied to hopping geometries from all methods collectively, ensuring a unified coordinate system for plotting. Analysis of the plot reveals a distinctive pattern: the transition geometries from the XMS-SA3-CASPT2 methods predominantly appear on the right side, while those from other methods are mainly situated on the left. This observation aligns with the fact that XMS-SA3-CASPT2 trajectories

rarely yield a significant percentage of the *trans*-stilbene isomer. Consequently, we infer that, in these reduced coordinates, the right side of the plot corresponds to transition geometries leading to DHP, whereas the left side predominantly represents the *trans* isomer.

Figure 8: Analysis of hopping geometries using MDS. The axes depict the most significant reduced coordinates identified by MDS algorithm for a combined set of geometries across all the methods. The resulting plot categorizes the geometries by method, each represented by a unique color.

3.3 Simulated time-resolved photoelectron spectra

Arguably, the most detailed insight into stilbene photodynamics is provided by time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy, recently conducted by three research teams. All three teams initiated the reaction with a 266 nm laser field, and the evolving system was then probed by 4.65 eV laser (Stolow group¹⁶), 9 eV (Wörner group³¹) and 21 eV (Suzuki group¹⁸).

The pump-probe signal stems exclusively from the excited state in the first case, while the interpretation of the latter two experiments requires consideration of reactants, intermediates, and products in both the ground and excited states. In our analysis, we will focus on the region 5-6.5 eV (Wörner data) and 3.0-6.8 eV (Suzuki data). In both cases, these signals are directly related to the stilbene in the excited state. Further, we analyze the region 7.0-7.5 eV and 7.5-7.8 eV. Here, the signal should be indicative of the DHP formation and, as we show, also the hot *trans* isomer.

The calculated photoelectron spectra for each electronic structure method are presented in Figure 9. As for the electronic populations, the calculated spectra exhibit discernible disparities across the various electronic structure methods utilized. The OM3-MRCISD, SA2-CASSCF, and XMS-SA3-CASPT2 dynamical calculations feature a brief 4 eV component, accompanied by a decay of the excited state component (6-6.5 eV) in about 400 fs while the XMS-SA2-CASPT2 calculations feature the 4 eV component throughout the simulation time. These results are consistent with the previous findings on the electronic populations.

The calculated spectra except for the XMS-SA2-CASPT2 methods are found to be in good agreement with the experiments. Figure 10 shows the integrated curves directly comparable with the measured data by Wörner and Suzuki. The integration range for the comparison with the experiment done by Suzuki were shifted by 0.1 eV due to the proximity to the negative part of the spectrum. These data indicate the excited-state lifetime of stilbene, once the system quenches to the ground state, these electrons with a low binding energy are no longer populated.

The experiments by Suzuki with the highest photon energy bear in principle the information on the emergence of the ground state products yet the interpretation is complicated as the fraction of excited molecules is unknown. The signal corresponding to the formation of DHP is estimated to peak at 7.1 eV.¹⁸ Therefore, we also integrated the spectra in the 7-7.5 eV range. The time evolution of this signal is similar for different methods, yet the signal on an absolute scale is larger for the XMS-SA3-CASPT2 method, in agreement with the higher

Figure 9: Simulated photoelectron spectra for surface hopping dynamics with various electronic structure methods; the intensities were included via Dyson norms. The pump-probe signal was calculated by subtracting the ground state signal at $t = 0$.

DHP formation. However, the signal is still present for the OM3-MRCISD and SA2-CASSCF methods, even though no DHP is formed.

The region 7.5-8.0 eV was assigned by Suzuki et al. as the ionization from the *cis*-stilbene in the S_1 state to a higher cation state. This is indeed what we observe in our simulations in the early stages. However, the signal is persistent even at the times when all the excited state population is dumped to the ground state. We then observe from our simulations that the

Figure 10: Integrated time-resolved photoelectron spectra. The first column presents the integrals of the calculated spectra from Figure 9 in the range 5 eV to 6.5 eV (blue line) along with the experiment (red line).³¹ The second column displays the integrated calculated spectrum (blue line) from 3 eV to 6.8 eV along with the corresponding experimental spectrum (red line). The third column is analogous to the second, with the energy range from 7.5 eV to 7.9 eV.¹⁸ The fourth column corresponds to the 7.0 eV to 7.5 eV that should be most sensitive to the DHP formation.¹⁸ All the integrals were convoluted with Gaussian function with a standard deviation of 30 fs. The comparisons with the experimental data are normalized to the maximum value.

7.5-8.0 eV pump-probe signal corresponds to the hot *trans*-stilbene formed once the excited state depopulates or to the DHP. Note that *trans*-stilbene has ionization energy somewhat lower than *cis*-stilbene.¹⁸

The calculated photoelectron spectra then reflect the time-dependent quantum yields. While the OM3-MRCISD method leads to a significant formation of the *trans*-stilbene, it shows little DHP-related signal. On the other hand, the XMS-SA3-CASPT2 method predicts

too much DHP and it fails short to describe the formation of *trans*-stilbene. However, it is very difficult to judge from the experimental spectra how much of the DHP was formed during the photochemical reaction. The signals assigned to DHP can also stem from the *trans*-stilbene formation.

3.4 Nonadiabatic simulations with a bias

The simulations of *cis*-stilbene photoisomerization have illustrated the critical impact of the electronic structure theory method on observable quantities. However, these simulations are computationally expensive, limiting our capacity to conduct a wide array of simulations with various electronic structure methods. Nonetheless, conducting a basic sensitivity analysis remains valuable.

One approach to navigate this challenge is to carry out the most efficient simulations, exemplified here by employing the semiempirical method with the OM3 Hamiltonian, supplemented by an additional potential to modify the potential energy surface. If then a small perturbation of the potential leads to a major change in the outcome, we are at least aware of the sensitivity issue. We have introduced a potential in the form of a simple harmonic oscillator, defined by the equation:

$$V(r) = \frac{k}{2}(R - R_0)^2 \tag{6}$$

In this expression, R represents the distance between carbons 2 and 2', as depicted in Figure 2, and k signifies the force constant measured in $\text{eV}\text{\AA}^{-2}$. The constant R_0 is set to 1.5 \AA to stimulate the DHP molecule formation; a higher force constant implies a stronger tendency toward closing the cycle.

The upper panel of Figure 11 demonstrates how the quantum yield of DHP varies with the force constant k . For small force constants, the DHP quantum yield is zero, consistent with the OM3-MRCISD simulations failing to capture its formation. However, there is a

sharp increase in the DHP quantum yield around $k=0.83 \text{ eV\AA}^{-2}$, indicating that the potential energy surfaces are biased enough to start pulling the molecule towards the DHP conical intersection. The lower panel of Figure 11 further illustrates the energetics of different stationary points on the potential energy surface when the bias is applied, with the excited state energy at the Franck–Condon (FC) point serving as a reference. Conical intersections positioned above the FC energy (marked by the dashed line) are energetically inaccessible. Following this logic, the population of *trans*-stilbene should diminish for k values exceeding roughly 1 eV\AA^{-2} , consistent with the observed quantum yields. Notably, the DHP quantum yield peaks locally and never reaches unity, indicating that the *cis* CI2 conical intersection remains energetically viable within the range of k values we have explored. The fate of the reaction is largely determined in the initial phase during the bifurcation into the cyclization or photoisomerization pathways.

Figure 11: Quantum yields of *cis*-stilbene photoproducts as a function of applied force constant. The upper panel shows the product ratio on the force constant k of the harmonic oscillator, as referenced in equation 6. The lower panel shows the energy difference between the Franck-Condon point (dashed line) and several conical intersections, also varying with different values of k .

Figure 12: Time-resolved photoelectron signals for the biased simulations. The left panel shows the generated spectra for the biased and unbiased simulations at the OM3-MRCISD level, while the right panel presents the corresponding integrals across different spectral ranges. The comparisons with the experimental data are normalized to the maximum value.

The biased simulations are further scrutinized in Figure 12 where we present the calculated photoelectron spectrum for the biased and unbiased cases. The upper panel illustrates the unbiased simulations, while the lower panel depicts simulations with a notably large value of $k = 0.83 \text{ eV}\text{\AA}^{-2}$, corresponding to a DHP quantum yield of 0.26. In the unbiased simulation, the entire wavepacket swiftly (within 200 fs) converges towards structures with larger C–C distances before gradually dispersing. Conversely, the bias compels molecules to close the cycle, yet some molecules still prefer photoisomerization. This difference is mirrored in the calculated spectra, with a stronger signal in the 7-8 eV region where the DHP signal increase becomes apparent in the biased simulation. Still, the general features of these very different simulations look similar.

Another significant disparity between the simulations is observed in the excited-state lifetime. The characteristic reaction time spans about 300 fs for the unbiased simulation, whereas it approaches 400 fs for the biased simulation with $k = 0.83 \text{ eV}\text{\AA}^{-2}$. The lifetimes calculated with the unbiased simulations with all electronic structure methods show too fast decay (if there is a decay at all), the present value for biased simulations is more consistent with the experimental observations.

4 Conclusion and Discussion

We have modeled the photodynamics of *cis*-stilbene with the fewest switches surface hopping or Landau–Zener surface hopping methods, focusing on the sensitivity of the nonadiabatic dynamics on the electronic structure level used. The differences were substantial: while for some approaches (XMS-SA2-CASPT2), no population transfer was observed within the first 500 fs, other methods agreed on the ultrafast dynamics being essentially complete on that timescale. The quantum yields for the different approaches were also very different. While the XMS-SA3-CASPT2/cc-pVDZ method showed a negligible *trans* isomer production and dominant DHP formation, the other methods indicated much lower DHP yields, a result

more consistent with experimental data in the liquid phase.

These discrepancies could hardly be seen just from inspecting the potential energy surfaces. The energetics for the different methods were not so distinct except for XMS-SA2-CASPT2, which appears as an outlier throughout the work, and comparable dynamics could be expected based on static investigations. Yet, qualitatively distinct dynamics were achieved only by changing the number of states we average over in the multi-reference methods, although stilbene is a molecule where state-averaging dependence would not be suspected.

The results show two critical points in the reaction mechanism. First, the initial bifurcation of the wavepacket into cyclization or photoisomerization pathways. Second, reaching the conical intersection to form DHP in the cyclization pathway. We conclude that none of the simulations are completely satisfactory. Most of the methods contradict the experimental photoelectron spectra indicating the presence of DHP in the early times of the dynamics, while the XMS-SA3-CASPT2 method overestimates the DHP formation. At the same time, all the electronic structure methods underestimate the excited-state lifetimes compared to the most recent experiments, yet agree with older measurements.

Suzuki et al. argued that photoexcited *cis*-stilbene favors ring closure over photoisomerization in the gas phase. This would indicate rather strong environmental effects – the ring closure is important in non-polar solvents yet by far not dominating over the photoisomerization. Our results indicate that the time-resolved data can be equally interpreted with a much higher *trans*-stilbene quantum yield. Thus, we conclude that none of the simulations can fully explain the photoelectron experimental spectra. What is the correct answer then? We believe that experiments focusing on geometrical features, such as ultrafast electron diffraction,⁵¹ rather than electronic quantities like photoelectron spectra might cut the Gordian knot.

Our study thus suggests that we should be more careful with the evaluation of nonadiabatic simulations. The usual strategy rests on mapping the potential energy surface with an expensive electronic structure method that is then used to validate an approach more amiable to nonadiabatic simulations with thousands of electronic structure evaluations. However,

such an approach does not seem to be satisfactory. While performing multiple simulations with different electronic structure methods is impractical, the dynamics with biases seem to be an alternative. Using a thrifty method such as the OM3-MRCISD approach with multiple biases can provide a hint at the potential problems with our calculations. Therefore, we propose a sensitivity analysis approach based on adding small perturbing potential into the system. Our simulations with a bias potential were able to bridge methods with negligible and dominant DHP formation helping us understand how much energy is necessary to transfer between these two frameworks. This strategy could certainly be refined to incorporate more nuanced considerations. Non-geometrical constraints, such as energy difference constraints or penalties explicitly targeting certain conical intersections, could be envisaged.

Incorporating perturbing potentials is a common tactic in computational statistical mechanics, akin to utilizing metadynamics.⁵² Similarly, empirical potentials have been employed to enhance photodynamical simulations by compensating for missing correlation energy,^{53,54} aligning with the principles of Δ machine learning. However, in this instance, our aim is solely to augment the system with an additional potential to evaluate the reliability of our computed results. One can think of changing the paradigm of these approaches and employing them in the sensitivity analysis business.

Armed with experimental data, we could contemplate designing additional potentials to optimize the agreement with experimental observations. In this scenario, quantum yields, excited state lifetimes, and time-resolved photoelectron spectra can be computed and compared with experimental data for any trajectory—whether unbiased or biased. The forces can then be adjusted to achieve the closest match with experimental findings. In our current study, we have utilized quantum yields as input, and the results exhibit a notably improved agreement with experimental data. This approach bears a resemblance to the construction of optimal pulses, and the technology of optimal control could be directly applied.

The field should also be in general more careful with the experimental interpretation. In biology, it is not common to stop whenever the hypothesis confirms experimental observation.

An alternative hypothesis is typically suggested, and the outcome is compared. We advocate for adopting this attitude even in the field of photodynamics.

Johannes Kepler in his essay on the six-cornered snowflake expressed the hope that truth could be uncovered by comparing many mistakes. We suggest that this might be the most productive approach also for the field of photodynamics.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Czech Science Foundation for the support via grant number 23-07066S. This work was supported by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. T. J. was additionally supported by the grant of Specific university researchgrant No A2_FCHI_2024_010.

Supporting Information Available

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TOC Graphic

